

Catalogue of Type Specimens in the amphibians and reptiles collection of the Museo de Biología, Universidad del Zulia (MBLUZ), Maracaibo, Venezuela

Catálogo de Ejemplares Tipo de la colección de anfibios y reptiles del Museo de Biología de la Universidad del Zulia (MBLUZ), Maracaibo, Venezuela

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ABSTRACT

We provide a complete and updated catalogue of the Type Specimens of the amphibians and reptiles collection of the Museo de Biología de la Universidad del Zulia (MBLUZ), Maracaibo, Venezuela. This collection contains a total of 23 type specimens (four Holotypes: one amphibian and three reptiles, and 19 Paratypes: five amphibians and 14 reptiles), representing 14 species. The taxa represented by these Types were described between 1996 and 2020. So far, only one of their names is regarded as a junior synonym (*Cryptobatrachus remotus* Infante-Rivero, Rojas-Runjaic & Barrio-Amorós, [2009]). The Type Specimens belonging to the families Strabomantidae, Hemiphractidae, Microhylidae (Anura), Sphaerodactylidae, Anolidae, Scincidae, Colubridae and Dipsadidae (Squamata), come mainly from western Venezuela and, to a lesser extent, from Caribbean islands, the Venezuelan coastal range, southern Venezuela and Colombia. An appreciable number of publications on amphibians and reptiles in Venezuela have been derived from this collection; however it faces serious infrastructure and security problems generated by the current institutional crisis of national universities, due to the unprecedented economic and social deterioration in the country.

Keywords: Amphibia, biological collections, Reptilia, taxonomy, zoological history.

RESUMEN

Se provee un catálogo completo y actualizado de los Ejemplares Tipo de la colección de anfibios y reptiles del Museo de Biología de la Universidad del Zulia (MBLUZ), Maracaibo, Venezuela. Esta colección contiene actualmente un total de 23 Ejemplares Tipo (cuatro Holotipos: un anfibio y tres reptiles y 19 Paratipos: cinco anfibios y 14 reptiles), representando 14 especies. Los taxones representados por estos Tipos fueron descritos entre 1996 y 2020. Hasta el momento sólo uno de sus nombres se considera un sinónimo junior (*Cryptobatrachus remotus* Infante-Rivero, Rojas-Runjaic & Barrio-Amorós, [2009]). Los Ejemplares Tipo pertenecientes a las familias Strabomantidae, Hemiphractidae, Microhylidae (Anura), Sphaerodactylidae, Anolidae, Scincidae, Colubridae and Dipsadidae (Squamata), proceden principalmente del occidente de Venezuela y en menor grado de islas del Mar Caribe, Cordillera de La Costa, Sur de Venezuela y Colombia. De esta colección ha derivado un número apreciable de publicaciones sobre anfibios y reptiles de Venezuela, no obstante afronta graves problemas de infraestructura y seguridad generados por la actual crisis institucional de las universidades nacionales, producto del deterioro económico y social sin precedentes en el país.

Palabras clave: Amphibia, colecciones biológicas, historia de la zoología, Reptilia, taxonomía.

INTRODUCTION AND HISTORY

The Museo de Biología de la Universidad del Zulia (MBLUZ) was established at the beginning of the 1980s. Although, Bisbal & Sánchez (1997) recorded that the Museo de Biología de la Universidad del Zulia (MBLUZ) was established in 1979, there is no documentary or factual evidence of that. We have been unable to document a proper date of foundation, for which reason we herein propose to take into consideration the earliest possible historical record in catalogue, represented by the date of collection of fish specimen No 1, obtained by ichthyologist José Moscó on September 11, 1980. Moscó began teaching at La Universidad del Zulia in 1979. He is considered the founder of MBLUZ and its first Director.

José Moscó, was a biologist graduated at the Universidad Central de Venezuela, where he was also a co-founder of its Museo de Biología (MBUCV). In 1979 he was employed at the Colegio Universitario de Carúpano (now IUT “Jacinto Navarro Vallenilla”), state of Sucre, when he was called to Maracaibo by Professor Víctor de Espinosa, then the Director of the División de Estudios Básicos Sectoriales of the Facultad Experimental de Ciencias, Universidad del Zulia (FEC-LUZ). So, he quickly came to FEC-LUZ to occupy the post left by American ichthyologist Donald C. Taphorn, who had indeed privately started a collection of fishes from the Lake Maracaibo basin. This primordial but important collection was donated by Taphorn to the Museo de Ciencias Naturales de Guanare (MCNG) at the Universidad Nacional Experimental de Los Llanos Occidentales “Ezequiel Zamora” (UNELLEZ) in Guanare, Venezuela, where he developed not only a lifelong successful career as a researcher and professor, but also founded a very important museum of natural sciences.

The MBLUZ harbors collections of fossils, plants, aquatic invertebrates, fishes, amphibians and reptiles and to a lesser degree, mammals, birds and arthropods. The latter three are just considered small reference collections of the local fauna. The amphibians and reptiles collection contains around 1,900 catalogued numbers (*ca.* 2,300 specimens), mainly from western Venezuela, particularly from the states of Zulia and Falcón, but also some specimens from other regions of the country, including the eastern Coastal Range, and some Venezuelan islands in the Carib-

bean Sea, including Isla de Margarita, La Blanquilla, and the archipelagos of Los Roques, La Orchila, Los Hermanos, Las Aves and Los Frailes. This collection is one of the smallest in the country in terms of diversity of species and number of samples from different bioregions; however, it contains material from some Venezuelan localities generally poorly explored, as well as some rare or unique taxa.

In recent times, the herpetological collection of MBLUZ increased in numbers and diversity thanks to collaborative agreements with other national research and higher education institutions, such as the Instituto Venezolano de Investigaciones Científicas (IVIC). Many of the samples lately recovered during MBLUZ-IVIC joint field activities came from some Venezuelan insular territories in the Caribbean and represent species otherwise rarely collected in the country, some of them still undescribed.

In its early times, the herpetological collection of MBLUZ was formed by sporadic captures made during field trips and practices of the zoology courses of the Departamento de Biología (FEC-LUZ), local research projects carried out by university professors and samples donated by students and researchers from other museums (*e. g.*, Barros *et al.* 1996, Barros 2000, Ugueto *et al.* 2007).

One of us (TRB), currently the Director of MBLUZ, began collecting amphibians and reptiles systematically as a biology student in the mid-1980s. So, he established the founding nucleus of the collections of the Herpetology Section, with the aid of other students, curators and professors, such as Ramón Acosta, José Moscó, John Moody, Sandra Azuero, Wilfrido Cabezas, Rosanna Calchi, Miguel Duarte, Carmen García, Alfredo Pérez, Nayibe Pérez and Ángel L. Viloría, among others.

The acquaintance of Á. L. Viloría with Mr. Cornelio Bravo, then a laboratory technician at the Facultad de Medicina of the Universidad del Zulia, who had been closely attached both personally and professionally to the late Dr. Adolfo Pons (1914-1982)¹, eventually led to the rediscovery of part of his snake collection, formerly stored at the Estación Biológica Kasmaera (on the Río Yasa area of the Sierra de Perijá, state of Zulia, Western Venezuela). Bravo and Viloría made efforts towards an agreement between the faculties of medicine and sciences, which facilitated the donation of the valuable remains of the Pons' Collection to the MBLUZ (see Pons 1965). These samples came to the latter at around 1986.

1 Adolfo Pons was a Venezuelan physician; an academic specialized in tropical medicine. He made relevant scientific contributions not only to the knowledge of tropical diseases endemic to the Lake Maracaibo basin, but also to the ethnography of the local aboriginal people of Western Venezuela, and notably, to the ornithology and herpetology of this region, especially of the Sierra de Perijá (northernmost Andes). His admirable collection of birds from the State of Zulia (*ca.* 8,000 specimens), at first kept separately at the three field stations he established for the Universidad del Zulia: Las Peonías Lagoon (N of Maracaibo), Zipayare (near the border between Zulia and Lara States) and Kasmaera (Río Yasa, Perijá range), was donated to the Museo de Historia Natural La Salle (MHNLS, Caracas) just after Pons' passing in 1982 (Ginés 1984).

As a result of research carried out by MBLUZ staff and agreements or exchanges with other institutions, its number of Types has increased between 2010 and 2017. This can be appreciated through reading the list of Type Specimens of the Venezuelan zoological collections provided by Bisbal & Sánchez (1997), where no Type Specimens of amphibian or reptile were recorded for MBLUZ. Another small collection of reptiles at the Universidad del Zulia is kept by the Centro de Investigaciones Biológicas (CIB) of the Facultad de Humanidades y Educación. It contains a series of lizards and snakes collected by Harold Molero, mainly as a product of field work for his thesis on the reproductive cycle and feeding habits of *Basiliscus basiliscus* (Molero 1981, 2018). It does not contain types.

An appreciable number of publications and theses on amphibians and reptiles in Venezuela have been derived from collections of MBLUZ, in spite of the economic, social and political situation over the last two decades in the country, coupled with unfavorable institutional conditions derived from pandemic confinement in recent years. Part of the university premises (LUZ), including the museum (MBLUZ), has suffered various transgressions, theft and looting, with the consequent deterioration of infrastructure and material collections. Since 2021, Type Material in the collections, among other material, has been evacuated to safer places. There have also been other efforts to safeguard biological and heritage material, as permitted, according to the possibilities of mobilization and availability of funds. Nevertheless, much of the collections still remains under risk, waiting to be salvaged and allocated to another facility.

On the basis of the above mentioned events, a call for national and international help and support is made to ensure the adequate preservation and safeguard of the biological collections of MBLUZ. Additionally, the following catalogue has been prepared, according to the recommendation of the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature (Chapter 16, Article 72, numeral 10, and recommendation 72F.4), which concerns the publication of information distinguishing the Type material held by institutions devoted to zoological taxonomy (ICZN 1999).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The sequence of the taxa follows Frost (2023) and Uetz *et al.* (2022) for amphibians and reptiles, respectively. For each species the following information is presented (when

available): scientific name, genus, species, author, year, holotype, paratype, catalogue number, sex, locality, collector, date of collection and current name. Brackets have been used to distinguish information inserted to complete some of the above data that does not appear either published in the original description or in the specimen's labels, including abbreviations, acronyms, omission or other pertinent information. Additionally, some comments on nomenclature changes, validity of the taxa, or any other information of interest, such as their conservation status may be included. When applicable, the collection that currently harbors the specimens is specified.

The correct acronym for the Museo de Biología de la Universidad del Zulia is MBLUZ, as stated by Sabaj (2020, 2022). Other collection abbreviations follow the same author, except for CIEZAH (Colección Herpetológica Regional del Centro de Investigaciones en Ecología y Zonas Áridas of the Universidad Nacional Experimental "Francisco de Miranda"; for examples see Mijares-Urrutia & Arends 1999 and Barros *et al.* 2007)².

RESULTS

CLASS AMPHIBIA

Family Strabomantidae Hedges, Duellman & Heinecke, 2008

Pristimantis turik Barrio-Amorós, Rojas-Runjaic & Infante-Rivero, [2008]: 79.

Holotype: MBLUZ 155 (male), Cueva del Agua (galería inferior de la cueva de la Pared Norte), Mesa Turik, municipio Rosario de Perijá, Sierra de Perijá, estado Zulia, Venezuela (10° 24' N, 72° 42' W), 1,700 m asl. 19 March 1991 by Á[ngel L.] Vilorio.

Remarks: the manuscript was accepted for publication on January, 16, 2008; therefore the correct date of the publication of this description is not the printed date in the journal (2007), but 2008. The location of this specimen is unknown. This Venezuelan endemic species is currently valid.

Pristimantis yukpa Barrio-Amorós, Rojas-Runjaic & Infante, [2008]: 84.

Paratypes (corrected to MBLUZ 151; see comments below): MBLUZ 023-025 (three adult females), Caño

2 Another collection representative of the fauna of western Venezuela is the Colección Herpetológica Regional del Centro de Investigaciones en Ecología y Zonas Áridas (CIEZAH) of the Universidad Nacional Experimental "Francisco de Miranda" (UNEFM), formerly kept in Santa Ana de Coro, but currently immersed in the Museo de la Estación Biológica de Rancho Grande (EBRG) near Maracay, Aragua state.

María Lionza, San José de Los Altos, municipio Jesús Enrique Lossada, Sierra de Perijá, estado Zulia, Venezuela (10° 41' N, 72° 26' W), 551 m asl. 10 March 1987, Ángel L.] Vilorio, R[ossana] Calchi and C[armen Z.] García.

Remarks: the manuscript of the description of this taxon was accepted for publication on January, 16, 2008; therefore the correct date of publication is not the printed date in the journal (2007), but 2008. Checking the museum catalogue, numbers **MBLUZ 023-025** belong to three different species (*Pipa parva*, *Pseudopaludicola pusilla* and *Leptodactylus* sp., respectively), with a different locality (Río Machango, Estado Zulia, Venezuela) from the one where the paratypes of *Pristimantis yukpa* (wrongly cited as **MBLUZ 023-025** in original description) have been collected. On the other hand, there are three individuals of “*Eleuterodactylus*” catalogued under number **MBLUZ 151** from the type locality of *P. yukpa*, with a note written in pencil that says “loaned to César Barrio on March 2, 2000”; therefore the true number of the three paratypes of *P. yukpa* housed in **MBLUZ** is 151, instead of **MBLUZ 023-025**. However and similar to that which occurs with the Holotype of *Pristimantis turik* (**MBLUZ 155**), the current location of the three specimens under number **MBLUZ 151** is unclear. It is currently a valid species with a geographic distribution in Colombia and Venezuela (Arias *et al.* 2023).

Family Hemiphractidae Peters, 1862

Cryptobatrachus remotus Infante-Rivero, Rojas-Runjaic & Barrio-Amorós, [2009] (not “2008”): 48.

Paratypes: **MBLUZ 154** (male), Cueva de Los Laureles, Socuy River (Limón River system, Lake Maracaibo Basin), municipio Jesús Enrique Lossada, Sierra de Perijá, Zulia State, Venezuela (10° 45' 04.00" N, 72° 27' 42.00" W), ±610 m asl. 20 December 1990, Tito R[afael] Barros.

Remarks: this species name is currently regarded as a junior synonym of *Cryptobatrachus pedroruizi* Lynch 2008 (Meza-Joya *et al.* 2021). The specimen is well protected and in good state of preservation.

Family Microhylidae Günther, 1858

Otophryne pyburni Campbell & Clarke 1998: 309.

Paratype: **MBLUZ 346**, Yapima, Vaupés, Colombia (01° 01' N–69° 27' W), 145 m asl. [05 April 1975 by Nate Waltz].

Remarks: the present specimen was obtained by exchange with the Amphibian and Reptile Diversity Re-

search Center, The University of Texas at Arlington (UTA). Its former catalogue number was **UTA 5352** [Field number NW 62] (Campbell & Clarke 1998). This specimen is well protected and in good state of preservation.

CLASS REPTILIA

Family Sphaerodactylidae Underwood, 1954

Gonatodes astralis Schargel, Rivas, Makowsky, Señaris, Natera, Barros, Molina & Barrio-Amorós, 2010: 329.

Paratype: **MBLUZ 931** (adult male), Serranía de Los Pijiguaos, 140 km southwest of Caicara del Orinoco, [Distrito Cedeño], estado Bolívar, Venezuela, 600 m asl. 31 March 1987, Ramón Rivero [field number RAR 554].

Remarks: the present specimen was obtained by exchange with the Museo de la Estación Biológica de Rancho Grande (EBRG). Its former catalogue number was **EBRG 2031** (Schargel *et al.* 2010). It is a valid species. This specimen is well protected and in good state of preservation.

Gonatodes naufragus Rivas, Ugueto, Schargel, Barros, Velozo & Sánchez, 2013: 6.

Paratypes (seven specimens, all from Venezuela): **MBLUZ 1010**, adult male from Playa Juan Gerardo, by Gilson Rivas, José Julián Rodríguez and Ronnis Guevara on 20 October 2010. **MBLUZ 1011**, female, between Playa Juan Gerardo and Playa El Barco, La Blanquilla (11° 53' 22.84" N–64° 37' 10.62" W) by Gilson A. Rivas, José J. Rodríguez and Ronnis Guevara. **MBLUZ 1012**, female, and **MBLUZ 1013**, hatchling, from Playa Piedra Ahogada, La Blanquilla (11°49'23.87"N–64°38'09.15"W), 10 m asl, obtained on 21 October 2010 by Gilson A. Rivas, José J. Rodríguez and Ronnis Guevara. **MBLUZ 1147**, male, on 1 February 2012 by Gilson A. Rivas, Angel Fernández, Jose J. Rodríguez and Jackeline Reid. **MBLUZ 1146**, juvenile, lomas de granito, La Blanquilla (11°51'53.42"N–64°37'25.41"W), 15 m asl on 25 January 2012, 5 m asl. by Gilson A. Rivas, Angel Fernández, José J. Rodríguez and Jackeline Reid. **MBLUZ 1148**, female, La Blanquilla (11°51'32.24"N–64°37'27.17"W), 20 m asl on 2 February 2012, by Gilson A. Rivas, Ángel Fernández, José J. Rodríguez and Jackeline Reid.

Remarks: the Holotype of this species was catalogued initially under number **MBLUZ 1009**, and later transferred to **EBRG (5224)**, as it appears in the original description (Rivas *et al.* 2013). Two specimens (**MBLUZ 1012-13**) are now housed in the Amphibian and Reptile Diversity Re-

Otophryne pyburni paratype from the Papurí River. This is a rare microhylid species that possesses a geographic distribution in southeastern Colombia, southern Venezuela, northeastern Brazil and the Guianas. This species is one of the three that conform the genus in Venezuela; however few specimens of this genus are housed in Venezuelan museums. The paratype MBLUZ 346 represents one of the few specimens of this species housed in a Venezuelan collection. Photograph by William W. Lamar.

Gonatodes naufragus, female paratype MBLUZ 1148. This lizard species was first discovered by P. Wagenaar Hummelink in 1940, again observed in 2010 and described in 2013. Photograph by Luis Alejandro Rodríguez J.

search Center, the University of Texas at Arlington (UTA). Currently a valid species. The specimens in MBLUZ are well protected and in good state of preservation.

Gonatodes rayito Schargel, Rivas, García-Pérez, Rivero-Blanco, Chippindale & Fujita, 2017: 553.

Paratypes (five specimens, all from Venezuela): **MBLUZ 283-1** (male), **283-2** (female), [La Gira, near town of Betijoque [municipio Rafael Rangel, estado Trujillo, Venezuela], 450–550 m asl. [15 December 1990 by Tito R. Barros]. **MBLUZ 828-1** (male), **828-2** (female): Hacienda La Onía, El Vigía, estado Mérida, Venezuela (08°35'48" N, 71°41'27" W; 150 m). [2 August 2004 by Tito R. Barros, Fernando Rojas-Runjaic and César Barrio-Amorós]. **MBLUZ 1398** (juvenile): near Cueva del Pirata, La Azulita, estado Mérida, Venezuela (08° 42' 47" N, 71° 26' 26" W, 1,030 m asl) (Schargel *et al.* 2017).

Remarks: currently a valid species. All five specimens in MBLUZ are safe and in good condition of preservation.

Family Anolidae Cocteau, 1836

Anolis anatoros Ugueto, Rivas, Barros, Sánchez-Pacheco & García-Pérez, 2007: 17.

Paratype: **MBLUZ 896** (adult male), San Isidro, estado Barinas, Venezuela [08° 50' 83" N, 70° 34' 23" W], 1,480 m asl. 10 June 2006, J[uan] M[anuel] Guayasamín and C[ésar] L[uis] Barrio-Amorós.

Remarks: **MBLUZ 896** was originally deposited at the Museo de Historia Natural La Salle, Caracas (MHNLS 17873), later donated to MBLUZ during the time one of us (GR) acted as curator in MHNLS, and finally transferred on 2007 to the Natural History Museum, London, under the catalogue number BMNH 2007.3 (now NHMUK). Species treated by some authors as *Dactyloa anatoros* (Nicholson *et al.* 2018). Currently a valid species.

Phenacosaurus tetarii Barros, Williams & Viloría, 1996: 3.

Holotype: **MBLUZ 215** (adult male), on the roads that lead to the Páramo del Tetari, Sierra de Perijá [municipio Machiques], estado Zulia, Venezuela (10° 06' 34" N, 72° 53' 00" W), 2,790 m asl. 24 October 1989, Ángel [L.] Viloría.

Remarks: species treated by some authors as *Anolis tetarii* or *Dactyloa tetarii* (Nicholson *et al.* 2018, Uetz *et al.* 2022). This specimen is in good state of conservations, although pale or colorless, perhaps due to the preservation technique initially applied to it.

Phenacosaurus euskalerruari Barros, Williams & Viloría, 1996: 16.

Holotype: **MBLUZ 308** (adult male), in the canyons of Mesa Turik, Sierra de Perijá [municipio Jesús Enrique Losada], estado Zulia, Venezuela [10°22' 23" N, 72°44'27" W], 1,600 m asl. 22 March 1991, Jon Ugarte.

Remarks: treated in recent literature as *Anolis euskalerruari* or *Dactyloa euskalerruari* (Nicholson *et al.* 2018, Uetz *et al.* 2022). This specimen is in good state of conservations, although pale or colorless, perhaps due to the preservation technique initially applied to it.

Family Scincidae Gray, 1825

Mabuya zuliae Miralles, Rivas, Bonillo, Schargel, Barros, García-Pérez & Barrio-Amorós 2009: 605.

Paratypes (three specimens, all from Venezuela): **MBLUZ 190** (female), Aractogba, Barí indigenous community, Serranía de Abusanki, Sierra de Perijá, municipio Machiques, estado Zulia, Venezuela [09° 34' 32" N, 72° 55' 15" W], 175 m asl. [10 August 1989 by Tito Rafael Barros]. **MBLUZ 254** (female), Frontalia, Río de Oro, municipio Catatumbo, estado Zulia, Venezuela, 75 m asl. [31 May 1990 by Tito Rafael Barros]. **MBLUZ 737** (male), Embalse de [Pueblo Viejo], [Parque Natural] Burro Negro, municipio Lagunillas, estado Zulia, Venezuela [10°10'58.0" N, 71°02'42.3" W], 60 m asl. [March 2003 by Alfredo Montilla].

Remarks: **MBLUZ 254** was sent in exchange to UTA, now it is catalogued as UTA 56691; **MBLUZ 190** was sent in exchange to EBRG, now it is catalogued as EBRG 5131 (Camargo & Bisbal 2016). Hedges & Conn (2012) erected the new genus *Maracaiba* to place this species, together with *M. meridensis* Miralles, Rivas & Schargel, 2005. **MBLUZ 737** was not properly handled when collected and its abdomen is broken (open). Its viscera are everted, as they were at the moment of preservation.

Family Colubridae Cope, 1886

Oxybelis rutherfordi Jadin, Blair, Orlofske, Jowers, Rivas, Vitt, Ray, Smith & Murphy, 2020.

Paratype: **MBLUZ 1268** [adult], between San Francisco de Macanao and Cerro Los Cedros, Isla de Margarita, [estado] Nueva Esparta, Venezuela (11° 01' 34" N, 64° 17' 30" W) by Gilson Rivas, Eusebio Millán, Ángel Fernández, and Reina Gonto on 10 October 2013.

Remarks: currently a valid species, probably with a wider distribution in northern Venezuela and East of the Andes (Jadin *et al.* 2020). **MBLUZ 1268** is in good condition of preservation.

Family Dipsadidae Bonaparte, 1838

Atractus turikensis Barros, 2000: 3.

Holotype: **MBLUZ 301** (male [adult]), campamento 1800, Mesa Turik, Sierra de Perijá, [municipio Jesús Enrique Lossada], estado Zulia, Venezuela (07°42' 50" N, 10°24' 00" W), 1,800 m asl, 20 March 1991, Ángel [L.] Viloría.

Paratype: **MBLUZ 302** (female [adult]), campamento 1800, Mesa Turik, Sierra de Perijá [municipio Jesús Enrique Lossada], estado Zulia, Venezuela (07°42' 50" N, 10°24' 00" W), 1,800 m asl, 20 March 1991, Ángel [L.] Viloría.

Remarks: the location of sample **MBLUZ 301** is currently unknown. **MBLUZ 302** is in good condition of preservation, except for a small piece of skin removed to illustrate the coloration pattern. Note that the legend of figure 1 in Barros (2000) states that the small piece of skin was taken from the holotype, however as it is mentioned by the author on page 4, figures 1 and 2 are based on paratype **MBLUZ 302**, as it is confirmed in this work. The Paratype housed in the Museo de Ciencias Naturales de Guanare, Universidad Nacional Experimental de Los Llanos Occidentales "Ezequiel Zamora" (MCNG 1914), was catalogued initially as **MBLUZ 303** and collected by Francisco Herrera.

Pseudoeryx relictualis Schargel, Rivas, Barros, Péfaur & Navarrete 2007: 237.

Paratype: **MBLUZ 895** [juvenile], near Bobures, municipio Antonio José de Sucre, estado Zulia, Venezuela (09° 14' 34" N, 71° 02' 29" W), [ca. 10 m asl], October 2004, Jacinto Sánchez.

Remarks: the Type Specimen was catalogued first in **MBLUZ** and later exchanged with the Amphibian and Reptile Diversity Research Center, The University of Texas at Arlington (UTA 54114), as it appears in the original description (Schargel *et al.* 2007). Currently a valid species.

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